

EXAMINING THE ROLE OF TYPE AND REASONS OF ACCESS TO DIGITAL CONTENT AND TEACHERS' SCAFFOLDING ON STUDENTS' ENGLISH LITERACY VIEWING SKILLS

Ma. Angel Uy-Carballo and Judith C. Chavez

Graduate School, Lourdes College, Inc., Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

In the digital age, exposure to English content through online platforms has become a focal factor influencing students' literacy development. This study investigated how the type of English digital content, purpose of digital engagement, and teachers' pre-viewing and while-viewing scaffolding strategies, and by examining the predictive influence on students' English literacy viewing skills of 293 community college students in Misamis Oriental. This study was anchored on two complementary theories which are Extramural English (EE) Theory and Vygotsky's Scaffolding Theory (ZPD), which explained how exposure and teacher support all contribute jointly to students' viewing skills as an English literacy macro-skill. The data were analyzed statistically using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques, including factorial ANOVA and regression analysis. Using a descriptive-correlational design, the research found that students frequently engage with entertainment and social media content, primarily to stay informed or improve their skills. While teachers heavily utilize pre-viewing and while-viewing scaffolds, regression analysis revealed that only the type and purpose of digital content, not scaffolding, significantly predict literacy levels. Students demonstrated high proficiency across all literacy dimensions, particularly in interpretation and inference. The study shows that the type of digital content and the intent behind accessing the content have a substantial impact on the English viewing literacy skill of the participants, which led to the rejection of both null hypotheses at the overall ANOVA level. However, when the results are considered at the post-hoc analysis, the low effect size and the limited number of significant differences indicate that though the nature and intent have some impact, it is limited to some categories. These results suggest that purposeful, diverse digital exposure is more influential than instructional support in modern literacy acquisition,

emphasizing a shift toward learner autonomy in digital environments. Future researchers may investigate the role of AI-supported learning tools in their potential function as mediators or substitutes for traditional teacher scaffolding in Digital environments. This study also suggests providing specific viewing guides, essential questions, and outcome-based tasks that require students to analyze, interpret, and evaluate content. Consider integrating purpose-driven digital viewing tasks in Teacher Preparation. Finally, to Strengthen Instruction on higher-order viewing literacy skills by emphasizing balanced instruction across all levels of viewing literacy.

Keywords: *extramural English, digital content, multimodal evaluation, teacher scaffolding, and viewing literacy.*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of digital and multimodal media has transformed the nature of literacy in the 21st century. The OECD (2023), in the PISA 2022 Results, reported continuing concerns about students' reading performance and emphasized the growing importance of evaluating online information and navigating digital texts critically. Recent research supports the potential benefits of extramural English exposure. Busby (2024) reported that early and sustained engagement with English outside school was associated with stronger vocabulary knowledge among university students. Similarly, Holsanova (2020) found that learners' strategies and purposes in extramural English activities influenced language-related outcomes.

This research is aligned within Sustainable Development Goal 4: Quality Education, which strives for inclusive and equitable quality access to learning opportunities and lifelong learning skills.

These gaps are particularly relevant in the context of a community college in Misamis Oriental, where students demonstrate frequent engagement with English digital media but where the relationship between such engagement, classroom scaffolding, and measurable viewing literacy outcomes remains underexplored.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following:

1. What type of English digital content do students view?
2. What is the students' purpose of access to English digital content?
3. What is the extent of teachers' use of scaffolding strategies in viewing-focused English lessons in terms of Pre-Viewing Scaffolds and While-Viewing Scaffolds?
4. What is the level of students' English viewing literacy skills in terms of Comprehension and Detail Extraction, Interpretation and Inference, and Critical/Multimodal Evaluation?
5. Do the type and purpose of digital content in English and teachers' scaffolding strategies significantly predict students' English viewing literacy skills?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. The descriptive component was used to summarize patterns in students' exposure to English digital content, teachers' scaffolding strategies, and students' English literacy viewing skills. The correlational component examined the relationships among the identified independent variables and the dependent variable using statistical procedures (Creswell and Creswell, 2021).

Participants of the Study and Sampling Procedure

The participants of the study were students enrolled in a community college in Misamis Oriental during the first semester of the Academic Year 2025–2026. A total of 1,245 students were enrolled in the Purposive Communication course during this period. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample of 293 students was determined and selected from four academic programs in the institution through random sampling. Data were gathered after the completion of the first semester, following the implementation of viewing-focused instructional practices.

Research Instrument

The study used an adapted survey questionnaire aligned with the research objectives and organized into three sections corresponding to the variables in the statement of the problem. Each variable was measured using 10 indicators rated on a 5-point Likert scale, while the viewing literacy component included performance-based items. Students' exposure to English digital content was adapted from Raonić (2021) and Luo et al. (2025). Teachers' scaffolding strategies were adapted from Richardson et al. (2021) and Domínguez and Svihla (2024), measuring pre-viewing and while-viewing instructional supports.

Students' English literacy viewing skills were measured using items adapted from established national and international frameworks, including the K to 12 English Curriculum Guide and Media and Information Literacy Curriculum Guide (DepEd, 2016; 2023), the NAEP Reading Framework, the PISA Reading Literacy Framework, and the RAND Reading Study Group model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What type of English Digital Content do students' view?

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the types of English digital content viewed by students. The overall mean of 3.00 ($SD = 1.331$) indicates that students' viewing preferences are moderately spread across the five categories. The results show that entertainment content is the most frequently viewed type, reported by

90 students (30.72%). This indicates that students' English exposure primarily occurs through leisure-oriented and socially interactive digital media.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Type of English Digital Content that Students' View

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Literary works	45	15.36
Social media content	83	28.33
News or informational	34	11.60
Entertainment	90	30.72
Educational Videos	41	13.99

Research Question 2. What is the students' purpose of access to English digital content?

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of students' reasons for accessing English digital content. The overall mean of 2.34 ($SD = 1.165$) falls within the category "School assignments".

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Reasons of Accessing English Digital Content

Description	Frequency	Percentage
To communicate w/ others	15	5.12
To be entertained	24	8.19
To stay informed	104	35.49
To do school assignments	54	18.43
To improve English skills	96	32.76

When viewed alongside Table 1, where entertainment and social media were the most frequently viewed types of content, the results suggest that students' viewing behavior and reported reasons for access may not always align directly.

Research Question 3. What is the extent of teachers' use of scaffolding teaching strategy in viewing-focused English lessons in terms of:

3.1 Pre-Viewing Scaffolds;

3.2 While-Viewing Scaffolds?

Table 3 presents the summary of *teachers' use of scaffolding strategies in viewing-focused English lessons*. The overall mean of 4.31 ($SD = 0.59$) is interpreted as High, indicating that scaffolding strategies are consistently practiced across instructional stages. Across the two dimensions, Pre-Viewing scaffolds obtained the highest mean ($M = 4.34$, $SD = 0.67$), while While-Viewing scaffolds recorded a slightly lower mean ($M = 4.28$, $SD = 0.61$). Although both dimensions fall within the High range, the small difference

of 0.06 suggests a slight emphasis on preparatory strategies before students begin viewing. This pattern indicates that teachers give considerable attention to preparing learners, such as activating prior knowledge and setting clear purposes, before engaging them with English digital materials. Prior research has noted that structured preparation can help learners approach multimedia input with clearer expectations and improved focus (Ramezanali et al., 2021).

Table 3
Summary Table of Scaffolding Teaching Strategy in Viewing-focused English Lessons

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Pre-Viewing	4.34	High	0.67
While Viewing	4.28	High	0.61
Scaffolding Teaching Strategy (Overall Mean)	4.31	High	0.59

Overall, the results show a consistent pattern of high-level scaffolding in both preparatory and real-time instructional phases. The slight variation between the two dimensions suggests a balanced approach with a modest emphasis on preparation. Research on multimedia learning environments likewise highlights the value of instructional guidance both before and during exposure to audio-visual texts (Etikan and Bala, 2019).

Research Question 4. What is the level of students’ English viewing literacy skills in terms of Comprehension and Detail Extraction, Interpretation and Inference, and Critical/Multimodal Evaluation?

Table 4 presents the summary of students’ English literacy viewing skills across three dimensions. Among the three dimensions, Interpretation and Inference obtained the highest mean ($M = 12.80$, $SD = 1.17$), which fell within the *Very High* range. This signified that students showed particularly strong ability to interpret implied meanings, draw conclusions, and establish logical connections from multimodal English texts. The difference of 1.63 between the highest and lowest means suggested a slight pattern in which higher-order interpretive skills were somewhat more developed than literal detail extraction skills.

Table 4
Summary Table of Students’ English Literacy Viewing Skills

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Comprehension and Detail Extraction	11.17	High	1.27
Interpretation and Inference	12.80	Very High	1.17
Critical Evaluation	11.99	High	1.82
English Literacy Skills	11.99	High	2.60

The overall pattern reflects consistent performance across all three dimensions, with no dimension falling below the High level. This distribution may relate to students’ continued

exposure to English digital materials and the structured instructional supports reported in earlier tables. Research in multimedia learning contexts has noted that guided engagement with digital texts can support both interpretive and evaluative skills (Ramezanali et al., 2021).

Research Question 5. Do the type and purpose of digital content in English and teachers’ scaffolding strategies significantly predict students’ English viewing literacy skills?

Table 5 presents the factorial analysis of variance results examining the effects of digital content and purpose of viewing on students’ English literary skills. The significance level was set at 0.05.

The result revealed that type of digital content significantly influences students’ English literary skills ($F = 2.574$, $p = .038$, $\eta^2 = .037$), suggesting that variations in the type of digital content viewed by students contribute to differences in literacy performance. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that digital content does not significantly influence English literary skills (H_02) is rejected. This implies that other factors may also play a role in shaping students’ literacy development. From a pedagogical perspective, exposure to educational digital materials supports language comprehension and reading engagement, particularly when the content is structured and academically oriented (Ertuğruloğlu et al., 2023).

Table 5
Factorial ANOVA Results on the Effects of Digital Content and Purpose on Students’ English Viewing Literacy Skills

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	Partial Eta Squared	Decision
Type of Digital_Content	63.532	4	15.883	2.574	.038	.037	Significant
Purpose	60.990	4	15.248	2.471	.045	.035	Significant
Type of Digital_Content × Purpose	138.195	13	10.630	1.722	.056	.076	Not Significant
Error	1672.522	271	6.172				
Total	380842.000	293					

*significant at .05

The purpose of viewing digital content significantly influences students’ English literary skills ($F = 2.471$, $p = .045$, $\eta^2 = .035$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis stating that purpose of use does not significantly influence English literary skills (H_03). This indicates that students’ motivation in using digital materials contributes to variations in literacy performance. However, the small effect size suggests that the practical influence of purpose of viewing is limited, implying that literacy development is shaped by multiple learning factors.

The interaction between digital content and purpose was not statistically significant ($F = 1.722$, $p = .056$), indicating that the combined influence of digital content type and viewing intention does not significantly affect students' English literary skills. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that digital content and purpose of use do not significantly influence English literary skills (H_01) is not rejected.

Table 6 presents the regression analysis examining whether teachers' scaffolding strategies significantly predict students' English literacy skills. The overall regression model was not statistically significant ($F = 2.968$, $p = .086$), with $R = .100$ and $R^2 = .010$, indicating that scaffolding explains only about 1.0% of the variance in English literacy skills; hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This suggests that teachers' scaffolding strategies, as measured in this study, do not significantly predict students' literacy performance. Studies published in 2020 and beyond indicate that while guided support enhances learner engagement, self-regulation, and confidence, its impact on standardized literacy performance is often mediated by learner autonomy and digital engagement behaviors (Kircaburun et al., 2020; Zhang and Liu, 2022).

Table 6
Regression Result on the Influence of Scaffolding Strategy on English Viewing Literacy Skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	37.865	1.117			33.913	.000
Scaffolding	-.442	.257	-.100		-1.723	.086
Model Summary						
R = 0.100	R ² = 0.010	Adj. R ² = 0.007	F = 2.968*	p = 0.086		

**significant at 0.05 level*

Conclusions

The study concludes that students' engagement with English digital content, particularly the diversity of content accessed and the intentional purposes behind its use was associated with variations in their English viewing literacy skills. Although teachers' scaffolding strategies were consistently practiced, they did not emerge as a significant direct predictor of literacy outcomes in the regression model. These findings imply that literacy development in contemporary classrooms extends beyond instructional delivery and is shaped by how learners independently engage with digital texts in their daily environments.

Pedagogically, the findings suggest that educators may benefit from integrating students' existing digital habits into structured literacy viewing instruction while encouraging purposeful engagement with English digital materials. At the same time, the modest explanatory power of the model indicates that English literacy development is multifaceted.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are thus offered to the identified sectors:

1. Students may use English digital media intentionally, not only for entertainment but also for learning, information gathering, and skill development.
2. Faculty and Instructors of a Community College teachers may provide specific viewing guides, essential questions, and outcome-based tasks that require students to analyze, interpret, and evaluate content.
3. Teacher Education Program of a Community College may consider Integrating purpose-driven digital viewing tasks in Teacher Preparation.
4. School Administration continue supporting the integration of authentic English digital media into the curriculum by providing resources and high-speed internet to teachers including the continuing provision of professional development workshops in multi-modal literacy and modern scaffolding techniques.
5. Future researchers may investigate the role of AI-supported learning tools in their potential function as mediators or substitutes for traditional teacher scaffolding in Digital environments.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors adhered strictly to established ethical standards to protect the rights, dignity, and welfare of the participants. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee before the conduct of the study, and formal permission was secured from the appropriate institutional authorities. The research was guided by the three core principles of the Belmont Report: Respect for Persons, Beneficence, and Justice, each of which was explicitly applied throughout the study. Through these measures, the study maintained ethical integrity, upheld participants' rights, and ensured compliance with institutional and national research ethics standards.

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